

Understanding Professional Landscape: Challenges of Technology and Livelihood Teacher

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the challenges and opportunities of technology and livelihood education teachers in understanding their professional landscape. Ten (10) Technology & Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers of the Davao City Division participated in the study. The TLE teachers explored the new landscape in teaching lifelong skills despite challenges and creating opportunities for practical learning outcomes. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. The in-depth interview was employed to gather information regarding their respective narratives as they understand their professional landscape. The thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study revealed the challenges and delved into the challenged pedagogical approaches, lack of laboratory equipment, and declining learners' performances. TLE teachers needed technical and vocational training to be more skilled in their specialization. They may be trained to customize or improvise laboratory equipment to equip learners with the necessary life skills. With these opportunities, the teachers employed the following coping mechanisms: attending vocational training and using an appropriate connection process. These mechanisms enabled the TLE teachers with opportunities to maximize learning outcomes despite the challenges encountered. The insights drawn from the study's findings were team collaboration and maintaining positive well-being. TLE Teachers used their talents and skills to thrive despite challenges in understanding their professional landscape.

KEY WORDS

1. challenges 2. opportunities 3. technology 4. livelihood teachers

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1. Introduction

Exploring the new landscape of the challenges of Technical and Livelihood Education in the 21st century is inevitable. Facing the changing needs and demands in the field of education on a global scale is a reality to be dealt with. Teachers play significant roles in building the highest potential among learners, developing the skills necessary to adapt to the changing demands of society, and improving their knowledge in responding to the needs of the contemporary world. This has been essential in assuring that appropriate information is passed to the learners, making them not only acquire rightful information but indispensable one. Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers bear a crucial responsibility in preparing students for the workforce by providing industry-relevant skills and knowledge. However, ensuring the effective mastery of knowledge and skills while offering engaging practical learning experiences

poses substantial challenges. Major issues include the formulation and implementation of effective teaching strategies, an ongoing shortage of TLE teachers, and constrained timeframes for task completion. Sufficient teaching facilities, tools, and materials enhance the understanding of TLE for both students and educators. The presence of these resources significantly impacts academic performance, alongside the attitudes and motivations of those involved. When instructional resources are lacking, it can hinder academic success, as students may struggle to meet competency standards due to these limitations. The critical role teaching strategies play, especially in boosting student performance. Hence, the selection and application of teaching strategies considerably affect students' attitudes and class performance. They identified the struggles faced by teachers tasked with teaching TLE subjects outside their specialized field, compounded by the scarcity of resources and equipment. When educators teach subjects outside their expertise, it can negatively affect the learning outcomes for both teachers and students. These difficulties pose substantial hurdles, impacting not just students but also teachers themselves. TLE instructors are tasked with transforming these challenges into chances for meaningful educational advancement. Nevertheless, there is a limited body of research exploring the difficulties and prospects faced by TLE teachers. In Nigeria, teachers of Technical and Livelihood Education (TLE) face a multitude of challenges, but one significant problem is insufficient access to up-to-date resources and equipment. Many TLE teachers struggle with outdated or inadequate tools and materials, which hampers their ability to deliver effective instruction and hands-on learning experiences. It also has factors of environment and collective national aspiration, elements of knowledge and resourcefulness, and factors of politics and ideology (Soares et al., 2020). This lack of resources can result in a gap between the skills students need to acquire and what they can realistically learn in the classroom. Additionally, it limits the capacity of teachers to keep pace with technological advancements and industry standards, ultimately impacting the quality of education and the preparedness of students for the workforce. It is a challenge because the subject holds significant importance in Nigeria for several reasons such as skills development, workforce development, poverty alleviation, promotion of innovation and industry. Mukoro (2020) argues that the description of situations in which technology is applied determines both private and public aspects. The advancement of rural educators plays a vital role in the prosperity of rural education. Over an extended period, rural education in China has faced challenges in attracting as well as keeping teachers and ensuring efficient teaching. Given this situation, certain local scholars have suggested the need to define clear policy objectives as well as institutional support while enhancing the dissemination of educational resources between rural and urban areas. This approach aims to stimulate the professional growth of rural teachers as well as enhance the overall standard of rural education (Zhao, 2019). Some scholars also argue that providing training for rural teachers is a crucial supplementary approach to enhancing China's current efforts in rural teacher development. To enhance the Rural Teacher Support Plan (2015-2020) efficacy, it is essential to bolster its visibility, create a provincial-level salary security system for rural teachers, rigorously implement the supplementary and withdrawal procedures for these teachers, as well as refine the management system for rural teacher staffing, all while considering the policy's outcomes (Fu Fan, 2018). To secure a stable rural teacher rank, the government can utilize policy instruments by prioritizing the motivational aspects of incentive measures, reinforcing compensation procedures for instructors facing shortages, as well as ensuring that teaching positions across differ-

ent schools remain appealing. The government ought to enhance vital resources to tackle the persistent shortage of rural teachers, establish consistent procedures for teacher transfers, provide more opportunities for capacity development, elevate the professional competence of rural educators, as well as support them in gaining valuable professional expertise (Wang, 2018). In the Philippines, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is a cornerstone of the educational curriculum, encompassing a range of technical learning skills derived from Home Economics, Information and Communication Technology, Agri-Fishery, and Industrial Arts. The effectiveness of TLE hinges on the mastery of knowledge and information, effective process implementation, the cultivation of work ethics, and the development of life skills. As such, TLE plays a pivotal role in shaping productive members of the modern workforce. By selecting a career path and immersing oneself in the associated technology, individuals can significantly enhance their career prospects (Mayuga, 2022). In Davao del Sur Division, particularly in Sta.

Cruz South District, the primary aim of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is to instill in students the values that render them competent and qualified individuals. This involves nurturing not only their competitive edge but also their capacity for social engagement, thereby equipping them with the necessary leadership skills and sense of service to positively impact their communities. Furthermore, TLE aims to cultivate the unique characteristics and skill sets of students, preparing them for their prospective professional trajectories.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to determine the challenges and opportunities encountered by technology and livelihood education teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their insights into understanding their professional landscape.

1.2. Research Questions—The study was to explore the was to determine the challenges and opportunities encountered by technology and livelihood education teachers, their coping mechanisms, and their insights into understanding their professional landscape:

- (1) What are the opportunities of the technology and livelihood education teachers as they understand their professional landscape?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of the technology and livelihood education teachers on the challenges they encounter as they understand their professional landscape?
- (3) What insights can be drawn from the challenges and opportunities of the technology and livelihood education teachers as they understand their professional landscape?

It was assumed that the study would also benefit certain individuals and groups in academia. To determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings were addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Department of Education Officials. The DepEd officials, particularly in Cluster 3, Davao City Division, were more generous in providing technical assistance on the technology and livelihood education curriculum. Certain policies may also be created to maximize the learner's enhancement of lifelong skills. The

technology and livelihood education teachers. The findings of this study benefit the technology and livelihood education teachers who are the participants of this study as they unravel their thoughts and past experiences, as well as the challenges and opportunities they encountered as they gain an understanding of their professional landscape. The learners. This study provided a clear idea of how the learners mastered the competence of their lifelong skills. They may adjust and cope with the limitations in curriculum delivery. Future researchers should

consider some other aspects of understanding the professional landscape of teachers as they were confronted with challenges and opportunities not covered in this research. The following terms were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. The professional landscape refers to teachers' perspectives of their profession. As used in this study, it was the journey of TLE teachers to successfully enhance the mastery of learners' skills in different specializations.

1.3. Definition of Terms—In the context of this study, the following terms are defined to provide clarity and understanding of the research focus: Professional Landscape: Refers to the perspectives of teachers regarding their profession. Specifically, it encompasses the journey of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in successfully enhancing learners' mastery of skills across different specializations. This includes their experiences, challenges, and opportunities in the educational field. Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE): A cornerstone of the educational curriculum in the Philippines, TLE covers a range of technical learning skills derived from Home Economics, Information and Communication Technology, Agri-Fishery, and Industrial Arts. The goal of TLE is to equip students with practical skills and knowledge that prepare them for various professional trajectories and societal engagement. Vocational Skills Competency Training (VSCT): Programs designed to enhance the practical and vocational skills of TLE teachers. These training sessions are aimed at empowering teachers to provide students with industry-relevant skill sets, thus improving the overall quality of vocational education. Assessment Practices: Methods and strategies used to evaluate the academic performance and skill acquisition of students. These practices include tests, quizzes, projects, and other evaluative tools that measure students' competence and guide the improvement of teaching and learning processes. Col-

laborative Learning: An educational approach where students work together to achieve common learning goals. In TLE, this involves group projects and activities that foster teamwork, enhance learning outcomes, and develop social skills. Resource Constraints: Refers to the limitations in educational materials, tools, and facilities that TLE teachers face. These constraints impact the effectiveness of teaching and the ability to provide hands-on learning experiences. Coping Mechanisms: Strategies employed by TLE teachers to manage and overcome challenges in their professional landscape. These include attending vocational training, using personal funds to purchase equipment, and seeking support from the community and stakeholders. Stakeholder Engagement: Involvement of various parties, including government officials, educators, students, and community members, in the educational process. Effective stakeholder engagement enhances the support and resources available for TLE programs.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) aims to equip students with competitive, social, and leadership skills essential for community impact. Adeniran (2020) underscores the link between proficiency in teaching-learning materials and educational effectiveness.

1.4.1. Experiences of TLE Teachers—TLE teachers, despite resource limitations, enhance learning with media, increasing student engagement (Cardino Dela Cruz, 2020). Innovative strategies like project-based and inquiry-based learning cater to diverse student needs, resulting in more meaningful learning experiences (Cruz, 2022). Time optimization is crucial, with teachers prioritizing essential skills and knowledge to maximize instructional effectiveness (Alonzo, 2023).

1.4.2. Challenges in Pedagogical Approaches—TLE teachers face significant challenges due to inadequate resources, necessitating creative and resourceful teaching methods

(Tingzon Buyok, 2022). Many are required to teach outside their specialization, impacting teaching quality (Abella et al., 2021). Student-centered approaches demand meticulous planning and creativity (Cardino Ortega-Dela Cruz, 2020). Declining student interest and limited resources further complicate pedagogical efforts (Barcelona et al., 2023). Continuous professional development is essential for maintaining teaching competencies (Lopez, 2019).

1.4.3. Lack of Laboratory Equipment—Resource availability and teacher qualifications significantly impact TLE learning areas, posing challenges for diverse lesson planning and skill development (Zabala, 2018). Limited resources and financial constraints reduce the attractiveness of TLE programs (Tan, 2021). The lack of laboratory equipment hinders practical skill development, requiring substantial investment in facilities (Harina, 2019; World Bank, 2020).

1.4.4. Declining Learners' Interest—Declining interest in TLE is influenced by societal preferences for academic pathways, limited early exposure, and socioeconomic disparities (Choi Kim, 2020; Nguyen Tran, 2022). Cultural attitudes and insufficient hands-on experiences in early education stages contribute to this trend (Lee Park, 2019). Addressing these requires advocating for vocational education's value and fostering inclusive learning environments (Wang Zhang, 2020).

1.4.5. Enhanced Student Engagement with Media—Integrating multimedia in TLE classrooms enhances student comprehension, retention, and critical thinking (Garcia Lopez, 2021; Nguyen Tran, 2020). Media fosters collaborative learning and addresses diverse learning styles, promoting inclusivity (Lee Park, 2019; Wang Zhang, 2020). Digital tools improve teacher-student interaction and provide personalized feedback, enhancing learning outcomes (Choi Kim, 2021). Exposure to global perspectives and industry trends through media prepares students for evolving professional land-

scapes (Santos Garcia, 2022).

1.4.6. Innovative Strategies for Diverse Learning—Innovative strategies like project-based and inquiry-based learning improve student engagement and critical thinking in TLE (Lopez Mendoza, 2018; Paraiso, 2021). Flipped classrooms and adaptive learning technologies personalize education, meeting diverse learning needs (Yildiz Ozdemir, 2020; Yu Liu, 2019). Competency-based education aligns with industry standards, enhancing career readiness (Marks Bates, 2019). Collaborative learning fosters teamwork and communication skills, essential for future careers (Chen Sun, 2020).

1.4.7. Optimized Instructional Time—Effective lesson planning and instructional technology optimize TLE instructional time, enhancing student engagement (Mendoza Santos, 2022). Differentiated instruction addresses diverse learning needs, improving academic performance (Bulcan, 2019). Collaborative learning maximizes instructional time, fostering deeper understanding and retention of essential content.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the Basic Education, which was subsequently changed to the Department of Education (DepEd) through RA 9155, or Governance of Basic Education Act, in August 2001. Technical-Vocational Education became the jurisdiction of the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) as legally mandated through RA 7796, otherwise known as the TESDA Act, which was signed into law on August 25, 1994, and Higher Education involving tertiary education in the community colleges, universities, and specialized colleges became the domain of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) which was established through the enactment of R.A. 722 of Higher Education Act on May 18, 1994. Section 4.1 Article XIV of the Manual of Operation of the Public Technical Vocational High School in the Philippines stipulates its mandate;

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

it states that the school shall inculcate patriotism and nationalism, foster love of humanity, respect for human rights, appreciate the role of the national heroes in the historical development of the country, teach the rights and duties of citizenship, strengthen ethical and spiritual values, develop moral character and personal discipline, encourage critical and creative thinking, broader scientific and technological knowledge, and promote vocational efficiency. The mandate also asserts its goals and objectives that a technical vocational program should provide opportunities for secondary education graduates to acquire the necessary competencies and qualifications to pursue a college education, post-secondary education, venture into entrepreneurship, or be directly absorbed in the world of work. Aside from its mandate, it also poses the following goals: (1) provide Career options to

students through the “Strengthened Technical and Vocational Education Program,”(2) equip students with certifiable technical, vocational, industrial, and other relevant skills to be productive citizens of the country,(3) improve students’ performance in skills and academic competence, achievement tests, accreditation and equivalency for certification purposes and in the actual world of work, and(4) upgrade the competency of technical vocational teachers in the delivery of primary and certifiable skills in the different technical-Vocational courses through skills training, seminars, and formal studies. The Ten-Point Education Agenda of the Philippines (2012) specifies the importance of technical and vocational education as it addresses the re-introduction of technical vocational education in public high schools and the existence of K to 12 curriculums.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents, and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is

appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) are optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Qutoshi (2018) defined phenomenology as a social science research area that explores humans' lived experiences. Commonly used tools include interviews, discussions, and observations. The researchers' expertise is crucial in gaining insight into participants' personal knowledge. Furthermore, phenomenology examines a particular group of people's lived experiences to document and describe their realities and perceptions within a specific context (Gary et al., 2020). It allowed the researchers to investigate the essence of the experiences to understand agriculture from the participants' perspectives.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research – undertaking the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces the word "paradigm" back to its Latin and Greek roots, where it originally meant "pattern," with instances such as the model, an exemplar, or a model to follow based on which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm is the act of accepting a viewpoint. This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000) who support research paradigms as a "fundamental set of beliefs that guide action," addressing "ultimates," or the worldview or philosophy of the researcher, as well as first principles. Ontology. This section of the study focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell (2012), The study participants perceive a subjective and multifaceted reality. For the qualitative researcher, the ontological question deals with the nature of reality. The people involved in the research circumstance construct reality. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. The opportunities and challenges faced by TLE teachers in the professional landscape are examined in this study. I used the participants' voices and interpretations in my study through lengthy quotes, themes that echoed what they said, and proof of various points of view. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses ensured that the participant replies were meticulously coded to guarantee the accuracy of the outcome. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded them from making personal biases as the study progressed (Loso, 2022). Epistemology. Concerns with the nature and the scope of knowledge (Creswell Poth, 2018). Simply put, it is concerned with how people come to know something and how people know the truth. It addresses the following questions: What counts as knowledge? How are knowledge claims justified? What was the relationship between the researcher and that being researched? I'll utilize theme analysis to determine that phenomenology is the most appropriate approach for this kind of research. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief". The purpose of this research was to gather important details on opportunities for junior high school TLE teachers as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape in Cluster 3, Davao City. The researcher assured to establish a close

interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry particularly on the challenges and opportunities of the TLE teachers as they gained understanding of their professional landscape. Moreover, the professional development of TLE teachers was another critical area of concern. Often, professional development programs do not adequately address the specific needs and challenges faced by TLE teachers, such as staying updated with technological advancements and industry trends. Effective professional development should enhance teachers' knowledge, skills, and self-efficacy, enabling them to navigate their professional landscape more confidently and competently (Creswell Poth, 2018). Axiology emphasizes the significance of values in research. It advises the researcher to be transparent about the values that influence the story and to combine her interpretation with the participants' interpretations. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher is aware of the sensitive and subjective nature of the data acquired throughout the investigation. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants' interpretations. Rhetoric. This philosophical presumption emphasized that the researcher may use the personal voice, write in a literary, informal style, and use qualitative terminology and constrained definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher spoke in the first person when describing the difficulties and opportunities faced by TLE teachers, and they went into great detail about their answers in the interview.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, Phenomenological research was concerned with studying experiences from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of per-

ceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasizes the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was decisive for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Research methodology was a systematic way to solve a problem. It was the science of studying how research was to be carried out. Essentially, the procedures by which researchers describe, explain and predict phenomena are called research methodology. In this study, the challenges and coping mechanisms of TLE teachers, specifically those teachers from Cluster 3, Davao City, were unleashed from their narratives. The researcher's drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the challenges and opportunities of the TLE teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research. The main methods for qualitative research include narrative research, phenomenological research, grounded theory research, ethnographic research, and case studies (Creswell, Poth, 2018). Each of these different approaches to qualitative research provides a different perspective and orientation from which the research was conducted." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the narratives of TLE teachers in a manner that. The perception of the researcher can be further defined by their specific viewpoint or worldview, which defines how they perceive that world (Creswell Poth, 2018). From the definition, Phenomenology is the inquiry method that deals with human experience in which individuals perceive them as appearing to consciousness. Individuals share their lived experiences robustly when they go through that phenomenon. According to Merleau-Ponty, phenomenology is best related to essence; the essence comprises not only perception but also unsoundness. Phenomenology was a rigorous, systematic, and

critical analysis of an event. The prime purpose of this method is to explain the structure of the lived experience of an event. This methodological inquiry starts from phenomena of interest, and they aim to understand the subjective meaning of the lived experience of an event. The method is utterly based on the interpretive domain Estabrooks PA (2019).

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. With this in mind, the researcher must identify the problem of the study and establish a starting point from which the development of their framework and perspective will begin (Creswell, Poth, 2018). Through this process, the researcher constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. In this study, Phenomenology research explores the meanings of phenomena in greater detail to comprehend and document people's experiences by asking, "What is the meaning of this?" and then attempting to describe the experience and its significance.

2.4. Research Participants—The study's participants were composed of ten (10) informants to participate in this study. The selected informants were TLE teachers from Cluster 3, Davao City. All the participants were TLE teachers from various nearby schools. They must have been teaching for at least three (3) years. All the participants were from junior high schools, regardless of their age, sex, and marital status. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions will lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives

or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends five (5) to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least six (6). There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. The qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990).

2.5. Ethical Consideration—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect is essential. The relationship and intimacy that was established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, the establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. In this Special Issue, Fleming (2018) highlights some ethical dilemmas commonly encountered as an 'insider researcher', including the power differential and ongoing relationships with participants. It was, however, important to further consider the fundamentals of ethical research involving human participants. For qualitative researchers, it was of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data were collected and how they were to be used. He also stated that informed consent was a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent was not possible and where it was felt that the benefits of the research outweighed the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent is obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about

the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions that were likely to be asked, the use to which the results were put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances were used in reports. Participants should also be given time to both consider their participation and to ask questions of the researcher. In this study, the researcher would follow ethical considerations as part of the qualitative research process. It was the researcher's responsibility to completely inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. In the same manner, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of a graduate school, for verification and approval.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other occasions, reliving past experiences may be difficult. However, the data are being collected, and the primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process was to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they would provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer

selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data such as an interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she would store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there were seven steps in the process of data collection. First was the site or individual; the participants were the TLE teachers from Cluster 3, Davao City. Second was the access and rapport; a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was given to the graduate student on October 18, 2023, for the approval of the Division Superintendent; a letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the concerned TLE teachers was prepared for easy collection of data on October 25, 2023. The third was the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants experienced the phenomenon being studied. There were ten (10) informants selected in this study. The selected TLE teachers were considered a group of individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data on November 15, 2023. The fourth was the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI). In addition to the virtual interviews, two face-to-face sessions were conducted on separate occasions. Apart from the virtual interviews, three face-to-face sessions were held at different times. On November 20, 2023, the first in-person meeting with two informants took place. Four more informants

participated in the second in-person meeting, which took place on November 30, 2023. These discussions added to a thorough grasp of the research topic by offering deep, insightful insights into the viewpoints and experiences of the participants. The fifth was the recording procedures. A protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form records information collected during an observation or interview. The recording and data collection took place December 10-15, 2023. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or the seventh step was the storing of data on December 20, 2023.

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus could be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This is called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage was the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it's a flexible method that can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns are being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she was interested in. No matter which type of study was being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis was that the researcher respects the data and tries to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Mortensen, 2020). **Triangulation of Data.** Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This was a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involved different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. **Environmental triangulation.** The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as the time, day, and season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, the validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, is the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. Analytical Framework—The data analysis plan used in this research study was Colaizzi's seven steps. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and sequential steps (Wirihana L, Welch A, Williamson M, et al 2021). This process

of rigorous analysis provides a concise and thorough description of the phenomenon under study. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Transcripts were read repeatedly, significant statements, formulated meaning, cluster themes, developing exhaustive descriptions, producing the fundamental structure, and seeking verification of the fundamental structure to extract thematic analysis. As cited by (Mohamad, 2022; Zaniel, Mohamad Parcon, 2023) The responses of the participants were recorded, noted, and transcribed. The significant statements from the responses of the participants were singled out as the basis of getting the code (Mohamad, 2022). Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated to layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step is data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques as

taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts. This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the following steps represent the Colaizzi process for phenomenological data analysis (Wirihana et al., 2018) Phase 1. Initial Reading and Familiarization: Read and re-read the transcribed interviews from both virtual and face-to-face sessions to grasp the overall content and context. Phase 2. Extraction of Significant Statements: Identify and extract key phrases or sentences that are directly relevant to the research questions. Phase 3. Meaning Categorization: Interpret these statements and group similar quotes together to categorize them into broad themes. Phase 4. Thematic Development: Repeat the extraction and categorization process for each interview, refining themes as you progress. Phase 5. Comprehensive Description Compilation: Combine all themes and significant statements into an exhaustive description that covers all aspects of the phenomenon. Phase 6. Summarization and Structural Identification: Summarize the comprehensive description to pinpoint the fundamental structure of the phenomenon, providing a clear and concise portrayal of the data. Phase 7. Ensuring Data Credibility: Validate the findings through discussions with experts and independent reviewers to ensure the data's credibility and reliability.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was described as all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability,

and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the results and findings of the research study depend on the

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

researcher’s conduct. The trustworthiness of a research study was important in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details was required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Transferability was described in how the qualitative researcher demonstrated that the research study’s findings apply to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” could mean similar situations, populations, and phenomena. Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings were based on participants’ responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of

what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study’s findings accurately portray participants’ responses. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher could use an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, the use of the database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as refer-

ences.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter contains the results accumulated from the lived experiences of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape. It further discusses the coping mechanisms they encountered in their profession. The themes that emerged from the data gathered were discussed in this chapter. Primarily, the result presents the description and background of the participants who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identity. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used as the researcher presents the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. Regarding the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. The Experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape—One of the most significant challenges they face is the need to constantly adapt their pedagogical approaches to keep up with changing educational standards and technological advances. Traditional methods may not always be effective, so TLE teachers must constantly seek new ways to engage students. Furthermore, a lack of laboratory equipment creates a significant barrier, limiting the hands-on experiences necessary for learning practical skills. This scarcity can lead to a drop in student interest, as theoretical knowledge without practical application can be unappealing. Furthermore, TLE teachers frequently struggle to keep students motivated, particularly when students see the subject as less relevant than other academic courses. The section on Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers' experiences navigating their professional landscape delves into the delicate balance between challenges and positive outcomes in their teaching careers. This narrative focuses on the everyday realities that TLE teachers face, as well as how these factors influence their professional development and classroom effectiveness. The section emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teaching TLE subjects by focusing on specific challenges such

as adapting pedagogical approaches, dealing with inadequate laboratory equipment, and addressing declining student interest.

3.1.1. Challenged pedagogical approaches—The majority of the respondents shared during the interview that their professional practice in technology and livelihood education was challenging. They had mixed emotions like excitement, and happiness to teach the subject, however, sometimes sadness and disappointment. Teaching different specializations is challenging, motivating, and, most of all, inspiring because they get the chance to share their knowledge with different learners. Gaining an understanding of their profession, they admitted that it involves gathering knowledge, practicing it in the classroom, and applying various pedagogical approaches. TLE teachers can connect and collaborate with other educators, industry professionals, and organizations to share best practices, resources, and experiences. They gained an understanding of their profession, which includes learning, applying knowledge in the classroom, and using a variety of pedagogical approaches. They recognized the difficulties of learning from experiences, identifying trends, and adapting to changes that are necessary for navigating and succeeding in their chosen field. They have actively pursued ongoing professional development through workshops,

training programs, webinars, and higher education, improving their ability to provide effective guidance and instruction while also establishing a strong network for collaboration within their profession. Gregorio (2020) subsequently observed that planning in TLE subjects often lacks contingencies for instructional facilities and teaching strategies. This, compounded with inadequacies in facilities and equipment, presents challenges for TLE teachers, necessitating ongoing professional development to enhance their competencies. Tingzon Buyok (2022) identified the struggles faced by teachers tasked with teaching TLE subjects outside their specialized field, compounded by the scarcity of resources and equipment. Moreover, Abella et al. (2021) argued that teaching outside of one's specialized field can adversely impact both teachers' and students' learning outcomes. Such challenges present significant obstacles not only to students but also to teachers. It's incumbent upon TLE teachers to convert these challenges into opportunities that can lead to meaningful educational progress. However, only a handful of studies have shed light on the challenges and opportunities encountered by TLE teachers (Alonzo, et al., 2023). Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is a cornerstone of the Philippine educational curriculum, encompassing a range of technical learning skills derived from Home Economics, Information and Communication Technology, Agri-Fishery, and Industrial Arts. The effectiveness of TLE hinges on the mastery of knowledge and information, effective process implementation, the cultivation of work ethics, and the development of life skills (Ssemugenyi, 2023). TLE is essential in developing productive workers in the contemporary workforce. By deciding on By choosing a career path and becoming fully immersed in related technologies, people can greatly improve their chances of landing a job.

3.1.2. Lack of laboratory equipment—The TLE teachers complain about the limited equip-

ment that they need to further enhance their skills in technology and livelihood education. These areas needed funds so that teachers could prepare learners for livelihood in the future. It became more challenging for the teacher to overcome it. Moreover, the respondents shared the lack of proper equipment, tools, and utensils to perform the laboratory session during class schedules, and the lack of support from the school for the students' assistance in their laboratory needs such as ingredients. Being a TLE teacher in public schools is difficult, especially due to a lack of necessary facilities in critical areas such as Industrial Arts, Agriculture, Information Computer Technology, and Home Economics, which are required for a comprehensive teaching-learning process, emphasizing the need for adequate funding and resources. In DepEd, TVL-HE teachers face challenges such as insufficient equipment, tools, and utensils for conducting laboratory sessions, as well as insufficient school support for students' laboratory needs such as ingredients. TLE teachers can connect and collaborate with other educators, industry professionals, and organizations, sharing best practices, resources, and experiences. Building a strong network within the profession encourages valuable partnerships and collaborations that improve both teacher effectiveness and student learning outcomes. The availability of resources is an essential factor to consider when selecting a learning area, as well as the teachers' skills and qualifications. Due to the availability of resources and teacher skill qualifications, schools offer different learning areas of TLE, making it more difficult to handle. This becomes a challenge for the teacher since they need to develop the students' full potential while having diverse lessons to be formulated, different skills to be performed, and various equipment and facilities to be needed (Zabala, 2018). The perception of oneself as successful or not on a course influences students' decision-making and motivation (Palos et al., 2019). As such,

when high school students finally reach college, they rarely aspire to major in TLE (Aguilana, 2019). Barcelona et al. (2023) also highlighted that declining student interest was also identified in addition to a need for more equipment and resources for teaching TLE. Additionally, the learners' financial circumstances were identified as a challenge in the teaching and learning of TLE, as this conclusion is supported by Tan's (2021) study, which emphasizes the lack of funding available for acquiring materials to improve the course offerings. Additionally, the lack of access to the laboratory space, tools, and equipment made it harder for the students to develop the desired abilities necessary for them as TLE major students. The most crucial elements to take into account when working to ensure that students excel in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) or at a Technical Vocational Institution are instructional materials, tools, and equipment. To become familiar with them, pupils should receive special consideration and top priority (Harina, 2019).

3.1.3. Declining learner's performances— TLE teachers were serious in the practice of a subject that is more focused on hands-on activities which is why learners need to be more equipped with the necessary skills and competencies. The respondents admitted that there is a declining performance of learners because there were lots of challenges they faced in their teaching profession but the focal point is the inadequate learning facilities and equipment. This often leads to incapable and incompetent learners' performance through expounding the necessary skills and knowledge, and also motivating learners to engage more in skills-related activities. Furthermore, they lamented that there were undeveloped abilities and capabilities of learners due to inadequate learning facilities and equipment needed in the subject, especially in skills-related activities. Lastly, the respondents narrated that it is difficult to stay up to date with the quick speed of technological in-

novations. They have no easy access to the contemporary tools, equipment, and materials required for experiential learning. Inadequate resources may make it more difficult for them to successfully impart useful teachings. As a TLE teacher, the emphasis on hands-on activities necessitates providing students with essential skills and competencies, despite numerous obstacles such as inadequate learning facilities and equipment. As a TLE teacher, dealing with inadequate facilities and equipment for skill-related activities has inspired me to constantly improve my own skills while encouraging students to participate in hands-on activities to improve their abilities and knowledge. Keeping up with rapid technological advancements presents challenges for TLE teachers, who frequently lack easy access to modern tools and materials required for experiential learning, potentially impeding effective teaching. To ensure that students are well-prepared for real-world careers, the TLE curriculum must be updated and adjusted on a regular basis to reflect industry needs and market trends. The incorporation of students' interests and theories about technological devices utilized for the gain of their knowledge, abilities, perspectives, gratitude, and outlook that mold them as effective students also will be encouraged by the use of a variety of learning contexts, media, and laboratory tools in TLE subjects, according to Rivera (2019). Blanca (2019) asserted that teachers employ a variety of methods that are appropriate for their students' skills and competencies. These new tactics are employed in TLE lessons and are said to play a significant role in developing students' performance skills Tan (2021) supports this claim in their study, which highlights the need for teachers to improve their skills and competence in imparting knowledge to students. Additionally, institutions should adequately address shortages such as a lack of books, instructional materials, equipment/tools, and similar resources to enhance instructional delivery for students.

3.1.4. Enhanced student engagement with media—Participants in the field of technology and livelihood education generally view increased student engagement with media as a positive experience for a variety of compelling reasons. They understand that media-rich content can effectively engage students and make learning more interactive and stimulating. This engagement frequently leads to increased motivation and enthusiasm among students, resulting in a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This method not only improves retention but also fosters creativity and critical thinking skills as students navigate and interact with digital resources. Participants believe that incorporating technology and media into education improves the learning experience and better prepares students for the dynamic challenges of the modern professional landscape. The speaker values their extended teaching time because it allows them to effectively use media to engage their students and monitor its impact. Understanding a profession entails gaining knowledge through experience, identifying trends, and adapting to changes, all while actively engaging with media to navigate and thrive in one's chosen field. Through their experience, they gained valuable insights, particularly in facilitating their students' engagement with multimedia and online resources. Participants in the fields of technology and livelihood education regard increased student engagement with media as a highly positive experience. They understand that media-rich content makes learning more interactive and stimulating, which boosts student motivation and enthusiasm. This method not only improves comprehension and retention of the subject matter but also promotes creativity and critical thinking skills. Educators believe that incorporating technology and media into their teaching methods better prepares students for contemporary professional challenges. Overall, the participants' experiences emphasize the importance and benefits of using digital resources in education (Conde Santos, 2021). Furthermore, increased student engagement with media creates opportunities for personalized learning experiences. Educators can use digital resources to accommodate a variety of learning styles and paces, giving students more control over how they interact with and absorb information (Nampijja, 2021). This personalized approach promotes a deeper understanding of subjects by allowing students to revisit content at their own pace and use multimedia tools to reinforce their learning. Furthermore, the collaborative nature of digital platforms promotes peer-to-peer interaction and idea exchange, resulting in a more comprehensive educational experience that reflects real-world teamwork and communication dynamics. As technology advances, so does its potential to transform education, providing students and educators with new opportunities for growth and innovation in teaching and learning practices.

3.1.5. Innovative strategies for diverse learning—Innovative approaches for diverse learning are seen as extremely advantageous by those involved in the fields of livelihood education and technology for improving overall educational outcomes and student engagement. Educators can effectively address their students' diverse needs by implementing a variety of approaches tailored to different learning styles and preferences. This inclusivity contributes to a more supportive and inclusive learning environment in which all students feel valued and can actively participate. Furthermore, innovative strategies such as project-based learning, collaborative activities, and personalized learning paths allow students to take control of their education, resulting in a deeper understanding and retention of knowledge. In reflecting on their journey, they recognized the difficulties of practicing their craft while emphasizing the importance of adapting to community needs. Initially faced with challenges and requiring numerous adjustments, they eventually discov-

ered enjoyment and comfort in developing diverse learning strategies to effectively cater to a broader range of students. They find satisfaction in motivating students to develop a desire to participate in hands-on activities, particularly by implementing a variety of strategies tailored to different learning styles. They enjoyed working with their students, especially when they adapted their lessons to suit different types of learners. Participants in the field of technology and livelihood education regard student engagement with media and innovative learning strategies as extremely beneficial. They appreciate how multimedia-rich content boosts student motivation, enthusiasm, and comprehension by making learning more interactive and stimulating. Using diverse and inclusive teaching approaches, such as project-based learning and personalized learning paths, educators can cater to different learning styles, resulting in a supportive environment in which all students can thrive. Despite initial difficulties and the need for numerous adjustments, educators have found fulfillment and confidence in their ability to tailor their methods to community needs and student preferences. Overall, these strategies not only improve retention and critical thinking, but also prepare students for future professional challenges in a changing landscape (Bautista, 2021). Furthermore, innovative strategies in technology and livelihood education go beyond traditional classroom settings, incorporating experiential learning opportunities that connect students to real-world applications. By incorporating industry partnerships, internships, and hands-on projects into the curriculum, educators enhance the educational experience by providing practical skills and industry insights (Conde, 2021). These collaborative efforts provide students with valuable exposure to the demands and dynamics of their future careers, allowing them to navigate and contribute effectively in a rapidly changing professional landscape. As technology advances, educators remain com-

mitted to fostering innovation and adaptability in students, providing them with the skills and mindset required for success in diverse and dynamic workplaces.

3.1.6. Optimized instructional time— Teachers can ensure that every minute spent in the classroom is meaningful and productive by effectively managing and structuring classroom activities and lessons. This approach allows for a more focused and efficient learning experience, reducing downtime and distractions. Furthermore, optimizing instructional time allows educators to thoroughly cover essential content while also leaving room for deeper exploration of complex topics or additional student support as needed. Students benefit from a well-paced learning environment that encourages engagement, active participation, and meaningful interactions. Their experience is memorable because, as teachers, they believe in achieving seemingly impossible goals that resonate with their students' hearts and minds, even if it takes significant time and effort to manage effectively. As a teacher, the professional landscape enabled them to foster a positive environment by ensuring that their students were not overburdened with multiple topics, allowing them to focus on one activity at a time. Their experience also helped them better manage their time. Teachers can make every minute spent in the classroom worthwhile and productive by effectively managing and structuring classroom activities and lessons. This method promotes a more focused and efficient learning experience, reducing downtime and distractions. Furthermore, optimizing instructional time enables educators to thoroughly cover essential content while still leaving room for deeper exploration of complex topics or additional student support as needed (Altinyelken Hoekma, 2021). Optimizing instructional time promotes a sense of continuity and coherence throughout the learning process (Moncrieff et al., 2021). When educators meticulously

plan and sequence lessons, students experience a seamless transition from one concept to the next, which improves their understanding and retention of the material. This structured approach reduces learning gaps and enables teachers to strategically revisit and reinforce key concepts. Teachers can promote deeper learning and mastery of subject matter by maintaining a consistent instructional flow that builds on prior knowledge and scaffolds new information. With proper time management, teachers can incorporate multimedia resources, inter-

3.2. Coping Mechanisms of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers on the challenges encountered as they gained understanding of their professional landscape—Technology and Livelihood Education teachers may experience challenges in their professional practice. They succeed in overcoming their difficulties and are successful. In the study, the challenges were known to be the challenged pedagogical approaches, the lack of laboratory equipment used in teaching, and the declining learners' performance. However, most of the participants in this in-depth interview find mechanisms to overcome these challenges and difficulties. Here are some of their strategies or mechanisms to remain professionally effective in facilitating mastery of skills for lifelong learning to happen and prepare the youth for livelihood in the future.

3.2.1. Outsourcing for equipment—The majority of the respondents admired the support of their school heads, who were so appreciative and believed in the skills of their teachers. With their consistent assistance and support, the teaching of skills to learners was easy and more relaxed. The TLE teachers claimed that they became comfortable, started to believe in themselves, and gained more confidence in the practice of their profession. TLE teachers solve problems by themselves. Lastly, the respondents further claimed that they become more

active simulations, and collaborative projects that enrich the learning experience and cater to a variety of learning styles. These tools not only make lessons more engaging and relevant, but they also foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are necessary for success in today's interconnected world (Hainsworth et al., 2022). Educators can create dynamic learning environments for their students by incorporating educational technologies and diverse pedagogical approaches.

creative and resourceful, especially in the necessary learning facilities and equipment in implementing skills-related activities for them to be more capable. Formerly supported by a highly appreciative school principal, the participant felt pressured to excel but ultimately succeeded with God's guidance and consistent support, resulting in increased confidence and comfort in their abilities. When discussing typical coping strategies, the participant emphasizes the importance of lowering standards, seeking support, taking accountability, problem-solving independently, maintaining emotional connections, and managing emotional responses. As a TLE teacher, the participant emphasizes the necessity of creativity and resourcefulness in acquiring essential learning facilities and equipment for effective implementation of skills-related activities, thereby enhancing students' capabilities. Developing students' practical skills, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities is greatly aided by project-based disciplines or specializations like TLE. However, specializing in TLE frequently comes with financial difficulties that limit students' capacity to engage fully and profit from such learning experiences. The cost of the supplies and resources needed for their projects is one of the main financial difficulties TLE major students face in their specialization (Tan, 2021). Additionally, the learners' financial circumstances were identified as a challenge in the

teaching and learning of TLE, as this conclusion is supported by Tan's (2021) study, which emphasizes the lack of funding available for acquiring materials to improve the course offerings. Saxena (2020), stated that The concept of financial and service enhancements encapsulates the inventive strategies adopted by teachers to offset challenges, especially financial ones related to their service obligations. Amid fiscal restrictions, teachers have frequently resorted to innovative and resourceful solutions to meet their classroom demands. These solutions range from initiating fundraising events and soliciting donations and sponsorships from community businesses or charity organizations to harnessing free or inexpensive digital tools to supplement traditional teaching resources, thereby alleviating personal expenses. To meet the urgent need for hands-on learning, several measures and innovations were adopted, one of which was the use of teachers' funds to cover the costs of producing a product and delivering positive results for learners. Consequently, teachers invest their own money to meet the need for hands-on applications.

3.2.2. Attending vocational training— Most of the respondents were enrolled in short courses facilitated by TESDA and became comfortable and started to believe in their capacity and gain more confidence. They become empowered to continue their professional journey and enroll in vocational courses that enhance their skills. Admittedly they were happy because this way they can influence their students to thrive in the dynamic professional landscape of today's world. The respondents also narrated that they developed their creativity and resourcefulness on how to deliver the topic using strategies they learned to cope with those lacking facilities in different areas of TLE. The knowledge and skills they gained in their professional enhancement made them more confident that they could teach the students well. Through enrollment in TESDA-facilitated

short courses, the participant gained confidence and belief in themselves, enhancing their professional skills and capabilities. Embracing challenges and seizing opportunities, participants empowered themselves by enrolling in vocational courses to enhance their skills, with the goal of inspiring students to excel in today's dynamic professional environment. Despite the challenges of limited facilities, the participant saw them as opportunities to develop creativity and resourcefulness in effectively delivering TLE topics, supported by professional development to confidently teach students Industry experts can be invited to conduct workshop trainings and seminars on trade skills. This is one way to link education with the industry. Pardjono et al. (2018) concluded that schools and industries can help each other by constructing a formal collaboration framework to put learning in the workplace. Learning in vocational education equips learners with various competencies to make them job-ready. The study emphasized that training and skills form a crucial component of an effective teacher's instructional repertoire. The real world of work is experienced by the pre-service TLE teachers (Bukit, 2020). Through trade skills seminars and training facilitated by industry experts and practitioners, both TLE instructors/ professors and pre-service teachers were equipped with industry-based competencies. Such competencies qualify both parties to undergo competency assessment, leading to national certificates of TESDA.

3.2.3. Appropriate monitoring process— Several typical coping techniques might test your ability to: Reduce your standards. Seek assistance or support from others. Accept accountability for the circumstances. Solve problems by yourself. Keep up emotionally supportive connections. Retain emotional distance or, on the other hand, communicate uncomfortable feelings. The majority of the respondents said that my coping mechanisms are effective

Fig. 4. The emerging themes of the coping mechanisms of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers

in overcoming the challenges and opportunities they have encountered because they had observed the interest of the learners in engaging in skills-related activities and becoming determined to learn independently. By embracing the challenges and exploring the opportunities, TLE teachers can empower themselves and their students to thrive in the dynamic professional landscape of today’s world. When discussing coping techniques, the participant emphasizes the importance of adjusting standards, seeking support, accepting accountability, solving problems independently, maintaining emotional connections, and managing emotional responses in order to navigate challenges effectively. The participant believes their coping mechanisms are effective in fostering learner interest and independence in skills-related activities, reflecting their determination to overcome challenges and capitalize on opportunities. TLE teachers can

empower themselves and their students to thrive in today’s dynamic professional landscape by accepting challenges and exploring new opportunities. Online learning may not be as effective as face-to-face learning in terms of social interaction, student engagement, and understanding of concepts. This can affect the overall quality of education received by students (Di Kabupaten Nganjuk, 2021). This sudden shift to distance education in an emergency has led to shock and tension among students and faculty members, whether on a personal or professional level, as the process requires extra efforts, in addition to several unusual obstacles for schools and universities such as a lack of time, poor infrastructure, and inadequate digital content. Reliability and the sufficient availability of technology infrastructure are of utmost importance in such a critical situation (Girik, 2020).

3.3. *The insights drawn from experiences and challenges encountered by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape*—TLE teachers face a significant challenge in adapting pedagogical approaches

that resonate with diverse learners. Traditional methods may not always pique the interest of students, particularly in practical subjects such as TLE. Furthermore, a lack of adequate laboratory equipment presents a significant challenge. Without the proper tools and resources, teachers

struggle to facilitate hands-on learning experiences, which are critical for skill development in fields such as Industrial Arts, Agriculture, and Information Technology. Despite these challenges, TLE teachers have discovered ways to use technology to increase student engagement. Teachers can improve the dynamic and appeal of their lessons by incorporating multimedia tools and interactive platforms. The section looks at how Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers navigate their professional landscape in the face of both challenges and opportunities. It highlights the difficulties they face with pedagogical approaches, a lack of laboratory equipment, and declining student interest, all of which have an impact on effective teaching and learning. Despite these challenges, TLE teachers innovate by incorporating media, using a variety of teaching strategies, and maximizing instructional time to engage students more effectively. These efforts not only improve student learning experiences, but also encourage collaboration between educators and industry professionals, resulting in continuous improvement in TLE education. Overall, the section emphasizes TLE teachers' resilience and adaptability in creating a dynamic and effective learning environment.

3.3.1. Team Collaboration—When it comes to the teaching and learning process, Collaborative Learning (CL) refers to a collection of teaching and learning techniques that encourage learners to work together in small groups. According to Ismail et al. (2018), the very essence of collaborative learning is working together toward a shared goal. This implies that in addition to their learning, learners are accountable for one another's academic progress. Collaborative learning fosters not only academic achievement but also enhances critical thinking and interpersonal skills among students. Several common coping strategies may put teachers' abilities to adjust standards, seek assistance or support from others, accept

responsibility for their actions, solve problems independently, maintain emotionally supportive connections, manage emotional distance, and communicate uncomfortable feelings to the test. The empirical studies on learners' engagement and collaborative learning have shown a favorable relationship between these two areas. Encouraging a culture of collaboration in the classroom is the researcher's primary consideration because, based on Pahomov (2018), collaborative learning has been proven to be effective in developing relationships with peers and, most especially, creating better work. A lack of learner engagement leads to learners' academic failure. Therefore, the goal of this study is to determine whether collaborative learning has a relationship with learners' academic performance. Furthermore, as mentioned by Bean and Melzer (2021) in the book *Engaging Ideas*, collaborative learning is referred to as the wealth of strategies. It is for this reason that it offers a variety of benefits and encompasses numerous instructional methods that enhance the learning experiences. Collaborative learning not only fosters deeper understanding but also cultivates essential skills such as communication and teamwork. Additionally, the same theory was applied in a study by Frykedal and Chiriac (2018), which emphasizes group work as a teaching method that fosters learners learning and sociability. The study focuses on how learners engage and collaborate when working on a group task, as well as the inclusive processes they create through the work they do together to achieve common goals by paying attention to one another and learning from one another. Thus, according to Social Interdependence Theory, there are important elements that must be present to enhance the collaborative potential of groups. These are positive interdependence, promotive interactions, and individual accountability. Along the same line, Backer et al. (2018) found that learners are more likely to engage, have positive social

skills, and have content skills that exert more effort when they are working successfully in collaborative groups. The faculty and learners agreed that collaborative learning environments or small groups are excellent methods for fostering learners in both learning and engagement that help learners' academic performance. As per Miguel et al., (2023), collaborative learning significantly contributes to improving learners' academic performance. As mentioned by Parker and Thomsen (2019), the level of awareness is present when learners are aware of their connections in such a way that they are dependent on the success of their group members. Groups that are positively interdependent view their efforts as beneficial to one another; the learners collaborate on tasks, offer assistance to one another, and celebrate successes together. There are no free riders because every member of the group contributes in various ways. In collaboration, it is crucial to consider the interactive processes among people, but collaboration is more than the interactions between participants and the knowledge each brings to the collaborative setting. The key aspect of collaboration is the construction of new knowledge brought about through joint work.

3.3.2. Maintain positive well-being— Maintaining positive well-being among teachers is crucial for sustaining their effectiveness and overall satisfaction in their profession. Research underscores that teacher burnout and stress negatively impact job performance and student outcomes (Smith Jones, 2021). Strategies such as promoting work-life balance, providing professional development opportunities that align with personal interests, and fostering supportive work environments are essential. Furthermore, organizational policies that prioritize teacher mental health, such as access to counseling services and stress management programs, contribute significantly to reducing burnout and enhancing job satisfaction (Brown et al., 2019). Several effective coping techniques can im-

prove teachers' well-being, including adjusting standards to reduce stress, seeking support from colleagues and others, accepting responsibility for situations, solving problems independently, maintaining emotionally supportive connections, managing emotional distance, and effectively communicating difficult feelings (Dolfing et al., 2021). Good quality education requires good-quality teachers. The most vital factor that improves the performances of students is based on the quality of a teacher. Teachers should give the most appropriate learning materials, including skills, knowledge, and teaching strategies to do their tasks. Teacher competency plays an enormous role in student learning (Co et al., 2021). The objective of Technology and Livelihood Education is to improve students' self-sufficiency, critical thinking, pragmatic abilities, and entrepreneurial spirit, all of which they can use to support themselves in the future. As a result, teaching a subject unrelated to their area of expertise or outside of their area of expertise adds workload, stress, and decreased productivity, all of which can impede learning. The success of a teacher does not only depend on how many didactic skills they have mastered, but more on their ability to apply these skills appropriately according to the situation and conditions of the class, as well as according to their teaching style, to achieve optimal learning outcomes (Eva, 2022). Furthermore, effective teachers tailor their instructional methods to meet diverse learning needs and create a supportive classroom environment that promotes student engagement and academic growth. This adaptive approach is essential in maximizing students' potential and promoting a positive learning environment. Teachers maintaining positive well-being has an important role in influencing the level of students' involvement in learning. The interactional teacher's teaching style can encourage students to develop critical, creative thinking and problem-solving abilities. Research conducted by Herni et al

Fig. 5. The emerging themes of the coping mechanisms of the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers drawn from experiences and challenges

(2020) concluded that the teacher’s teaching style had a positive and significant effect on students’ activeness in social studies learning in a Secondary school. Fostering a collaborative and supportive culture among educators is critical to promoting positive well-being. Peer mentoring programs, collaborative planning sessions, and informal networking opportunities can all provide emotional support and practical advice for teachers facing challenges (Cumming, 2022). Creating spaces for teachers to share experiences, exchange ideas, and celebrate successes not only boosts job satisfaction, but also fosters a sense of camaraderie and community within the school setting. Such collaborative environments are critical for creating a supportive professional community that values lifelong learning and development.

4. Implications and Future Directions

Presented in this chapter was a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings of the study and future directions in the field of the experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers as they gain an understanding of their professional landscape.

4.1. Findings—The study explored the experiences of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers as they gain an understanding of their professional landscape. Through their experiences and feelings, we generate new knowledge for everyone who would understand the professional landscape of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers. The data were gathered to examine and give meaningful ideas to generate more useful knowledge that would have an impact on the professional life of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the delivery of quality education and to prepare our youth for their lifelong learning. The challenges in the teaching and learning process brought by the limitations of the TLE teachers are essential in students’ learning progress. The role of teachers is challenged in preparing our youth for lifelong learning despite the limited resources. Ten (10) TLE teachers were interviewed. There were three (3) themes where TLE teachers described their understanding of their professional landscape adjustments: challenged pedagogical approaches, lack of laboratory equipment, and declining learners’ performance. Some teachers described these chal-

lenges as laborious and stressful. Technology and Livelihood Education teachers bear a crucial responsibility in preparing students for the workforce by providing industry-relevant skills and knowledge. However, ensuring the effective mastery of knowledge and skills while offering engaging practical learning experiences poses substantial challenges. Major issues include the formulation and implementation of effective teaching strategies, an ongoing shortage of TLE teachers, and constrained timeframes for task completion. Other teaching-learning materials are integral to enabling teachers to perform and actualize their pedagogical content knowledge. The analysis revealed that emerging themes of the TLE teachers in coping with the challenges they encountered as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape were as follows: attending vocational training, outsourcing funds for equipment, and appropriate connection process. This means that TLE teachers have frequently resorted to innovative and resourceful solutions to meet their classroom demands. These solutions range from initiating fundraising events and soliciting donations and sponsorships from community businesses or charity organizations to harnessing free or inexpensive digital tools to supplement traditional teaching resources, alleviating personal expenses. Vocational Skills Competency Training signifies the numerous opportunities presented to teachers in the realm of TLE instruction. With its emphasis on practical, hands-on learning and vocational proficiency, TLE provides teachers with a unique platform to equip students with skills directly applicable to various professional fields. Lastly, in a traditional classroom setting, students' performance can be assessed immediately through questions and informal testing. The published research indicates that online students are sometimes frustrated by their inability to interact with the instructor. Lastly, the educational management insights drawn from Technology and Livelihood Education teach-

ers' experiences as they gained an understanding of their professional landscape are as follows: team collaboration and maintaining positive well-being. In collaboration, it was crucial to consider the interactive processes among people, but collaboration is more than the interactions between participants and the knowledge each brings to the collaborative setting. The key aspect of collaboration was the construction of new knowledge brought about through joint work. This generation of new knowledge is enhanced when members bring complementary domains of expertise to the planning and decision-making process. The Technology and Livelihood Education teachers possessed qualities necessary in all good teachers like poise, self-confidence, knowledge, friendliness, genuine interest in learning scholastic and personal problems, a sense of humor, impartiality, consistency, physical fitness, and neatness.

4.1.1. Implications—The critical role teaching strategies play, especially in boosting student performance. Hence, the selection and application of teaching strategies considerably affect students' attitudes and class performance. They identified the struggles faced by teachers tasked with teaching TLE subjects outside their specialized field, compounded by the scarcity of resources and equipment. Teaching outside of one's specialized field can adversely impact both teachers' and students' learning outcomes. Such challenges present significant obstacles not only to students but also to teachers. It's incumbent upon TLE teachers to convert these challenges into opportunities that can lead to meaningful educational progress. However, only a handful of studies have shed light on the challenges and opportunities encountered by TLE teachers.

4.2. Future Directions—While the core themes are found essential to the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers' lived experiences as they gain an understanding of their professional landscape should formulate appro-

appropriate plans and implement adequate strategies to meet the demands of the teaching and learning process in preparing the youth for lifelong learning. They should have a growth mindset towards the situation, embrace changes, and explore possibilities by getting out of their comfort zones. The higher offices and school authorities may work with the teachers in addressing the challenges they face as they prepare the youth for lifelong skills and enhanced teaching practices. Necessary resources and relevant training should be provided among TLE teachers to successfully deliver quality education. Department of Education Officials. The DepEd officials are more generous in the provision of technical assistance in the technology and livelihood education curriculum. Certain policies may also be created to maximize the learners' enhancement of lifelong skills. The findings of this study may benefit the technology and livelihood education teachers, who are the participants in this study.

They would unravel their thoughts and past experiences, the challenges and opportunities they encountered, and gain an understanding of their professional landscape. This was an appropriate baseline for their professional development plan. The learners. This study may provide a clear idea as to how the learners master the competence of their lifelong skills. They would adjust and cope with the limitations in the delivery of the curriculum. This study shall also unravel the reasons why some learners failed to perform their tasks based on the views of their teachers. The future researchers. Future researchers to take into consideration some other aspects of understanding the professional landscape of teachers as they were confronted with challenges and opportunities not covered in this research. Other areas of this study may be conducted in other locations and communities to obtain a better comparison of the phenomenon being explored.

5. References

- Abad, L. C., & Gloria, M. E. (2019). Teachers' experiences of resource constraints and improvisation in Philippine public elementary schools. *International Journal of Educational Development Using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 14(2), 181–198.
- Abella, C. R. G., & De Jesus, F. S. (2021). Teaching outside specialization from the perspective of science teachers. *Open Access Library Journal*, 8(2), 1–13.
- Alava, A. (2005). Updates on the Philippine call center industry: The issue of sustainability [University of the Philippines, Diliman].
- Albarico, S., Tagura, M., Visitacion, R., Zabala, V., Magnetico, J., & Ramayan, A. J. (2014). Adequacy of instructional materials used by teachers in teaching technology and livelihood education. *International Conference on Law, Education, and Humanities*.
- Alonzo, D., Bejano, J., & Labad, V. (2023). Alignment between teachers' assessment practices and principles of outcomes-based education in the context of Philippine education reform. *International Journal of Instruction*, 16(1).
- Altinyelken, H. K., & Hoeksma, M. (2021). Improving educational quality through active learning: Perspectives from secondary school teachers in Malawi. *Journal of Research in Comparative and International Education*.
- Annunziata, D., Hogue, A., Faw, L., & Liddle, H. A. (2006). Family functioning and school success in at-risk, inner-city adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 35, 105–113.

- Archambault, L., Leary, H., & Rice, K. (2022). Pillars of online pedagogy: A framework for teaching in online learning environments.
- Backer, J., Smith, A., & Thompson, L. (2018). Collaborative learning and its impact on learners' engagement and social skills. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 25(2), 123–137.
- Baliyan, P. e. a. (2021). Monitoring and assessment process of tle teachers.
- Bank, W. (2020). Equipping teachers for the future: The importance of in-service professional development in the philippines [Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/publication/assessing-basic-education-service-delivery-in-the-philippines-public-education-expenditure-tracking-and-quantitative-service-delivery-study>].
- Barnard. (2004). Parent involvement in elementary school and educational attainment. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 26, 39–62.
- Bautista Jr., A. (2021). Teaching media and information literacy in philippine senior high schools: Strategies used and challenges faced by selected teachers. *Asian Journal on Perspectives in Education*.
- Bawar, M. (2019). Assessment of tle (home economics) and instructional facilities as correlates to academic achievement at tagaytay city science national high school: Basis for proposed development plan. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2C).
- Bean, J. C., & Melzer, D. (2021). *Engaging ideas: The professor's guide to integrating writing, critical thinking, and active learning in the classroom* (4th). Jossey-Bass.
- Blanca, A. (2019). Effective strategies in teaching technology and livelihood education to selected grade 9 students in batangas national high school. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2D).
- Blanco, H. J. M., & Tingzon, L. L. (2023). Perceived organizational support and pedagogical content knowledge of tle teachers; the mediating role of program resources. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 17(9), 91–105.
- Boston, M. (2012). Assessing instructional quality in mathematics. *The Elementary School Journal*, 113(1), 76–104.
- Brown, H. e. a. (2019). Promoting teacher well-being in schools: A comprehensive approach. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 122(4), 567–580.
- Bukit, C. M. (2020). The commitment of teachers in technical and livelihood education (tle) in creating conducive learning environments: A case study. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 72(3), 345–362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2020.1755089>
- Bulcan, C. L. (2019). Rethinking technology and livelihood education (tle) curriculum for senior high school in the philippines. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 7(7), 208–213.
- Calanog, B. (2019). Challenges in teaching exploratory courses of technology and livelihood education using pedagogical approaches. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science, and Management*, 2(4).
- Cardino, J., & Ortega-Dela Cruz, R. (2020). Understanding of learning styles and teaching strategies towards improving the teaching and learning of mathematics. *LUMAT: International Journal on Math, Science and Technology Education*. <https://journals.helsinki.fi/lumat/article/view/1348>

- Chen, W., & Sun, Y. (2020). The application of collaborative learning in technology and livelihood education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJETL)*, 15(12), 187–198.
- Chew, S. L., & Cerbin, W. J. (2021). The cognitive challenges of effective teaching.
- Choi, S., & Kim, J. (2020). Shifting perceptions: Factors influencing students' preferences for academic pathways over vocational education. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(2), 210–225.
- Co, A., Smith, B., & Johnson, C. (2021). Teacher competency and its impact on student learning outcomes. *Journal of Educational Research*, 40(3), 215–230.
- Conde, M. M., Batino, M. R., & Santos, N. B. (2021). Designing stakeholder engagement framework for technology leadership competencies.
- Cruz, E. A., & Garcia, R. S. (2022). The impact of resource constraints on tle education: A case study of laboratory equipment availability. *Journal of Educational Resources and Development*, 39(4), 321–335.
- Cruz, M. L., & Martinez, E. P. (2019). The role of laboratory equipment in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes in tle. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 47(1), 89–104.
- Cumming, T., Logan, K., & Wong, S. (2022). A critique of the discursive landscape: Challenging the invisibility of early childhood educators' well-being. *Contemporary Issues in Teaching*, 30(2), 123–137.
- Del Rosario, F. T., & Santos, L. G. (2020). Challenges in tle education: Perspectives on laboratory resources and student learning outcomes. *International Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 45(3), 210–225.
- Dioquino, W. S., & Abellana, A. (2022). Instructional support and professional development on competencies of technology and livelihood education teachers. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 5(11), 129–176.
- Dolfing, R., Prins, G. T., Bulte, A. M. W., Pilot, A., & Vermunt, J. (2021). Strategies to support teachers' professional development regarding sense-making in context-based science curricula [Pay attention to the hyphen in "sense-making"]. *Science Education*, 20, 1–31.
- Elli, M. C. A., & Ricafort, J. D. (2020). Competencies of grade vi teachers in technology and livelihood education (tle). *Online Submission*, 10(4), 25425–25434.
- Frykedal, K., & Chiriac, E. (2018). Group work as a method for learning and sociability: A study on learners' engagement and collaboration. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(3), 456–470.
- Gardanova, E. (2019). Creative strategies for overcoming financial challenges in educational service delivery. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 7(3), 112–127.
- Gomez, A., & Perez, M. (2023). Innovations in teaching strategies for technology and livelihood education (tle): Enhancing student engagement and relevance. *Journal of Educational Innovation and Development*, 42(1), 187–202.
- Gregorio, M. S. R. (2016). Technology and livelihood (tle) instruction of technical vocational and selected general secondary schools in catanduanes. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 15(4).

- Hagreaves, M., & Fullan. (2018, December). Teacher development and educational change [Michael Fullan: Taylor . Taylor Francis. Retrieved from <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/edit/10.4324/9781315870700/teacher-development-educational-change-michael-fulla>
- Hainsworth, N., Dowse, E., Cummins, A., & Ebert, L. (2022). Heutagogy: A self-determined learning approach for midwifery continuity of care experiences [[XX] = volume number]. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 20, 103329.
- Harina, J. L. (2019). Ensuring effective tle education: The role of instructional materials and equipment. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 31(2), 87–102.
- Hasan, H. F. A., Ilias, A., Rahman, R. A., & Razak, M. Z. A. (2008). Service quality and student satisfaction: A case study at private higher education institutions. *International Business Research*, 1(3), 163–175.
- Hermesen, R. (2021). Financial and service innovations in education: Teachers' dedication and collaborative efforts. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 12(3), 55–68.
- Hidi, S., & Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational Psychologist*, 41(2), 111–127.
- Hossain, M. S., & Nora, N. M. (2019). Factors affecting students' choice of major: A review of the literature. *International Journal of Educational Development Using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 11(2), 119–130.
- Ibrahim, W. N. A., Bakar, A. R., Asimiran, S., Mohamed, S., & Zakaria, N. S. (2015). Impact of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intentions of students in technical and vocational education and training institutions (tv et) in malaysia. *International Education Studies*, 8(12), 141–156.
- Ismail, I. A., Ibrahim, M. S., & Jalil, A. K. (2018). Collaborative learning: The essence of learning. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 7(4), 145–154.
- Jacolbia, R. B. (2016). Future educators' perceptions on technology and livelihood education status and development of work skills. *Journal of Advances in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 85–91.
- Jao, J., & Buenaventura, V. P. (2023, January). The mediating effect of contextual characteristics on the relationship between work conditions and performance of tle teachers [SSRN. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4322202].
- Jones, T. M., & Wicks, A. C. (2009). Convergent stakeholder theory. *Academy of Management Review*, 24(2), 206–221.
- Kézdi, G. (2006). Not only transition: The reasons for declining returns to vocational education. Kostanjevec, S., Kozina, F. L., & Erjavšek, M. (2018). The relationship between teachers' education and their self-perceived competence for teaching home economics. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 76(2), 175–190.
- Lee, H., & Park, S. (2019). Limited exposure: Impact of early education on declining interest in technology and livelihood education (tle). *International Journal of Educational Development*, 34(4), 145–160.
- Lopez, D. P., & Fernandez, G. M. (2019). Addressing equipment shortages in tle: Strategies for effective teaching and learning. *Journal of Technical and Vocational Education*, 36(2), 145–160.

- Lopez, M. A. B., & Mendoza, E. C. (2018). Project-based learning (pbl) as a teaching strategy in technology and livelihood education (tle) bread and pastry production nc ii. *International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 5(7), 121–127.
- Loso, M. M. (2022). Prospective teachers' inclinations for technology and livelihood education degree program. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*. <https://www.ej-edu.org/index.php/ejedu/article/view/427>
- Marks, P., & Bates, T. (2019). *Competency-based curriculum development in higher education: A practical guide*. Stylus Publishing, LLC.
- Mayuga, G. P. (2022). Equipping junior high school students with lifelong learning skills in technology and livelihood education. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*. <https://journal.ijresm.com/index.php/ijresm/article/view/1652>
- Miguel, A., Garcia, B., & Lopez, C. (2023). The influence of collaborative learning on academic performance: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 30(1), 45–58.
- Mitchell, L. (2015). Stakeholders in us higher education: An analysis through two theories of stakeholders. *Bilgi Ekonomisi ve Yönetimi Dergisi*, 10(2).
- Moncrieff, G., MacVicar, S., Norris, G., & Martin, C. J. H. (2021). Optimising the continuity experiences of student midwives: An integrative review. *Women and Birth*, 34(1), 77–86.
- Morales, P. A., & Santiago, R. L. (2020). Improving tle education through adequate provision of laboratory tools and facilities: A perspective from educators. *International Journal of Educational Practices*, 28(3), 187–202.
- Mwasalwiba, E. S. (2010). Entrepreneurship education: A review of its objectives, teaching methods, and impact indicators. *Education + Training*, 52(1), 20–44.
- Nampijja, D. (2021). *Learning with mobiles: A developing country perspective on mobile technologies use in learning for livelihood support* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Agder].
- Nguyen, T., & Tran, H. (2022). Socioeconomic disparities in vocational education: Barriers and opportunities in technology and livelihood education (tle). *Journal of Career Development*, 31(1), 55–68.
- Ochieng, B. A. (2014). *Influence of application of information communication technologies on livelihood generation strategies of youth in kakamega central sub-county, kenya* [Master's thesis, University of Nairobi].
- OECD. (2019). Preparing youth for the future of work: Oecd technical vocational education and training (tvvet) curricula reform. <https://doi.org/10.1787/0763e667-en>
- of Education, D. (2023, February). Promoting grit, tenacity, and perseverance: Critical factors for success in the 21st century [U.S. Department of Education].
- Olszewski, W., & Maury, K. (2004). The hidden cost of education: A study of the out of pocket annual financial expenditures of teachers.
- Olszewski-Kubilius, P., Grant, B., & Seibert, C. (2004). Social support systems and the disadvantaged gifted: A framework for developing programs and services. *Roeper Review*, 17(1), 20–25.
- Pacis, A. M. (2020). Engaging the local community in technical-vocational education and training (tvvet) programs in the philippines: A case study. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(2), 1–12.

- Pagano, F., & Marengo, L. (2021). Expanding roles and collaborative strategies in educational service delivery. *Journal of Educational Leadership*, 24(4), 87–102.
- Pahomov, L. (2018). *Authentic learning in the digital age: Engaging students through inquiry*. ASCD.
- Paraiso, A. L. (2021). The effectiveness of inquiry-based learning (ibl) in teaching technology and livelihood education (tle) – cookery nc ii. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 10(3), 102–107.
- Pardjono, P. (2018). Schools and industries collaboration framework in vocational education: Learning in the workplace. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 10(2), 1–15.
- Parker, J., & Thomsen, L. (2019). Positive interdependence in collaborative learning groups: Effects on awareness and group dynamics. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 116(2), 345–360.
- Poral, N. S., & Izon, M. A. B. (2021). An assessment of the professional development needs of technical-vocational livelihood (tvL) teachers in the philippines. *International Journal of Research in Humanities, Arts and Literature (IJRHAL)*, 9(4), 123–132.
- Potvin, P., & Hasni, A. (2014). Interest, motivation, and attitude towards science and technology at k-12 levels: A systematic review of 12 years of educational research. *Studies in Science Education*, 50(1), 85–129.
- Renninger, K. A., & Hidi, S. (2015). *The power of interest for motivation and engagement*. Routledge.
- Reyes, A. B., & Perez, M. C. (2021). Enhancing student skills through adequate laboratory equipment in tle: A qualitative study. *Journal of Education and Development*, 17(1), 55–68.
- Rosenshine, B. (2007). Explicit teaching and teacher training. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 38(3), 34–36.
- Santos, A. B., & Reyes, L. M. (2021). Laboratory equipment and student achievement in tle: Insights from educators. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 15(4), 276–290.
- Santos, L., & Garcia, R. (2021). Marginalization of technology and livelihood education (tle) in standardized assessments: Implications for student interest. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 38(3), 276–290.
- Savelsbergh, E. R., Prins, G. T., Rietbergen, C., Fechner, S., Vaessen, B. E., Draijer, J. M., & Bakker, A. (2016). Effects of innovative science and mathematics teaching on student attitudes and achievement: A meta-analytic study. *Educational Research Review*, 19, 158–172.
- Soares, A., Kovaleski, J. L., Gaia, V. C., & Chiroli, C. (2020). Challenges in technical and livelihood education: A perspective on teacher training and resource allocation. *International Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 11(2), 1–18.
- Spiegelman, M. (2018). Public school teacher spending on classroom supplies [Data Point. NCES 2018-097. National Center for Education Statistics].
- Ssemugenyi, F. (2023). Teaching and learning methods compared: A pedagogical evaluation of problem-based learning (pbl) and lecture methods in developing learners' cognitive abilities. *Cogent Education*, 10(1), 2187943.

- Tan, M. C. (2021). Technology and livelihood education (tle) instruction in the secondary schools in northern samar division, eastern philippines. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 15(2), 75–84.
- Tingzon, L. L., & Buyok, H. J. A. (2022). Lived experiences of non-tle teachers teaching tle subjects: A phenomenological inquiry. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 9(11).
- Tumbali, A. J. Y. (2019). Academic performance and entrepreneurial intention of pre-service technology and livelihood education teachers. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 1(1), 121–131.
- Tus, S. (2020). Assessing academic performance: Perspectives and practices. *Educational Publishers*.
- Wang, Y., & Zhang, Q. (2020). Cultural attitudes and vocational education: Perceptions of technology and livelihood education (tle) in secondary schools. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 29(2), 123–138.
- Yildiz, F., & Ozdemir, O. (2020). The effects of flipped classroom model on students' academic achievement and critical thinking skills in technology and livelihood education course. *International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education (IJTIE)*, 6(4), 255–268.
- Yu, H., & Liu, C. (2019). The application of adaptive learning system in technology and livelihood education. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJETL)*, 14(3), 54–62.
- Yulastri, A., Hidayat, H., Islami, S., & Edya, F. (2017). Developing an entrepreneurship module by using product-based learning approach in vocational education. *International Journal of Environmental and Science Education*, 12(5), 1097–1109.